

The mobilisation of trace elements through chloritization

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Recent studies highlight how the stability or breakdown of certain minerals control the mobilisation of specific trace elements during metamorphism. For example, Sn and W are primarily hosted by micas, hence, their mobilisation into the melt is controlled by micas' stability fields (Kunz et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2022). Similarly, peritectic cordierite and garnet (formed at different pressures) sequester different trace elements (Ballouard et al., 2023). Studies have thus far focussed on constraining the optimal melting conditions required to form granitic bodies with economic deposits. However post-emplacement retrogression, including the replacement of biotite by chlorite, may also be important for mobilising trace elements in migmatitic or granitic lithologies.

We compared two key migmatitic samples: one with exclusively fresh biotite, and the other with about 80% replacement of biotite by chlorite. Bulk-rock data were used to determine compositional differences between the two samples. The pressure and temperature conditions during chloritization were estimated using chlorite thermometry and phase equilibria modelling. Breakdown reactions were balanced in order to estimate the necessary influx of fluid for chloritization. Lastly, we used In-situ LA-ICP-MS trace element data and phase proportions from SEM maps to verify if the mass difference between the samples is entirely due to the chlorite-replacement reaction, and not due to protolith differences. Our results provide insight into the trace element redistribution during chloritisation of biotite, between chlorite and other minor products of the reaction (muscovite, ilmenite, and rutile). Our results show that although some elements are retained, others leave the system, thereby offering the potential to concentrate in shallower crustal levels.

References:

Kunz et al. (2022), *Geology* 48, 967-960.

Zhao et al. (2022), *Geology* 50, 121-125.

Ballouard et al. (2023), *Contributions to Mineralogy and Petrology* 178, 1-24.

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